

ULTRASONIC STRUCTURAL HEALTH MONITORING OF CFRP BY USING NOVEL OPTICAL FIBER SENSING SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Ultrasonic structural health monitoring (SHM) of composites are traditionally achieved by using piezoelectric sensor that has high sensitivity albeit with several disadvantages including bulk size, heavy weight and susceptibility to electromagnetic interference. In order to solve these problems, researchers found optical fiber sensors have high potential as an alternative if their performances (sensitivity, bandwidth, robustness, etc.) could be improved firstly.

In this report, we proposed several novel optical fiber sensing systems and applied them to ultrasonic SHM of carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP). Unlike traditional technique based on fiber Bragg grating (FBG) and tunable laser source, our novel systems use FBG or phase-shifted FBG and erbium fiber laser. The novel systems not only have high sensitivity and broad bandwidth, but also have their own unique characteristics. By changing the structures, the systems can detect ultrasonic signal and quasi-static strain simultaneously, or can detect ultrasonic signal but be immune to environmental condition change. The performance of these sensing systems were verified and demonstrated in a series of acousto-ultrasonic testing on a quasi-isotropic CFRP laminate. One system worked well in temperature change from 25 °C to 85 °C; the second one achieved static/dynamic measurement simultaneously; the third one had the highest sensitivity and bandwidth. All these techniques make the sensing systems ideal for practical ultrasonic SHM of CFRPs. If these techniques are utilized in practices, safety of composites is expected to improve.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials, such as carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRPs), have been widely used in many different areas. However, the inside micro-damages decrease the feasibility of such material, leading to the requirement of structural health monitoring (SHM) techniques. Compared to static SHM technique, e.g., measurement of static strain, ultrasonic SHM techniques provide more useful information inside the material where static measurement are unable to detect. Furthermore, ultrasonic SHM has possibility to discriminate composite damage types among delamination, matrix crack, fiber breaking, debonding, etc., and also has possibility to quantitatively evaluate these damages.

High-performance sensors are essential to achieve precise ultrasonic SHM, because the used ultrasonic signals always have low energy and high frequency. Conventional piezoelectric-based sensors have many advantages, yet their disadvantages are also obvious. Although bulk size and heavy weight can be partially solved by using more advanced sensors, such as PZT wafer, macro fiber composite and so on, their inability of embedding and susceptibility to electromagnetic interference are always problems. On the other hand, optical fiber sensors (OFSs) could perfectly solve these problems owing to their inherent physical properties, i.e., small diameter and direct strain encoding.

Nowadays, many different ultrasonic OFSs have been proposed and demonstrated based on different concepts [1]. Among these techniques, fiber Bragg grating (FBG) sensor are attracting most attentions and have already been used in ultrasonic SHM – active acousto-ultrasonic detection and passive acoustic emission (AE) detection – after their sensitivity and bandwidth are improved further. Nevertheless, their multiple sensitivity to strain, temperature and ultrasound requires feedback

controllers in conventional OFSs in order to compensate the influence from environmental static changes. This problem hinders the application of ultrasonic OFSs in SHM, especially in SHM of composite that usually suffers large environmental temperature or strain changes when this kind of material is used in airplane.

In this paper, we firstly introduce some state-of-the-art ultrasonic OFSs and their applications in SHM of composites in section 2. Next, several novel sensing systems based on FBG and erbium fiber laser (EFL) are discussed in section 3. Their practical applications are then demonstrated in section 4. Lastly, a brief conclusion and a long-term perspective are discussed in section 5.

2 STATE-OF-THE-ART ULTRASONIC OFS TECHNIQUES

Herein we mainly introduce the state-of-the-art ultrasonic OFSs based on FBG techniques. According to previous researches [2], the effective grating length of the FBG determines the upper limit of detectable frequency of ultrasonic waves. In order to maintain precise detection, FBG with short grating length was used, leading to low sensitivity because of the relatively low slope in its spectrum [3]. Recently, we applied phase-shifted FBG (PSFBG) in ultrasonic SHM, which was manufactured by inserting a phase shift in the middle of the grating area, as shown in Figure 1(a). Because the light is concentrated in the phase shifted area, short effective grating length and ultra-steep slope (Figure 1(b)) are simultaneously satisfied, meaning broad ultrasonic bandwidth and high sensitivity that makes the PSFBG be an ideal ultrasonic sensor. Based on this PSFBG, we designed a balanced demodulation technique to improve the sensitivity about 30 dB further [4]. The detection system is shown in Figure 1(c). Unlike other techniques those only use transmitted light or reflected light, both lights are detected by a balanced photo-detector (BPD) in our design. Because the wavelength of a tunable laser source (TLS) is precisely located on the 3-dB position of the PSFBG spectrum, the detected light power is changed by the Bragg wavelength shift of the PSFBG when the sensor is influenced by ultrasonic wave. Finally, the voltage change from the BPD corresponds to the ultrasonic signal.

Figure 1: PSFBG balanced sensing system: (a) phase shift in PSFBG; (b) the spectrum of PSFBG; (c) the schematic diagram of the system.

We then explored the application of PSFBG in both active and passive ultrasonic detections on CFRP laminate. Particularly, we obtained some interesting results in AE detection [5, 6]. Figure 2 shows the experimental setup of a tensile test to demonstrate PSFBG's performance. We glued our novel sensor and conventional PZT sensors to the laminate, as well as strain gage to detect AE signals and monitor reference strain level, as shown in Figure 2(a) and (b). Figure 2(c) shows the FBG attachment method. Figure 2(d) shows the final damage stage in a CFRP. Figure 3 shows the cumulative AE signals after certain data process method. From the curve of AE hit obtained by the PSFBG sensor, we demonstrated Kaiser Effect and discriminated signals generated from matrix cracks and fiber breakings, as shown in Figure 4(a) and (b), respectively.

Figure 2. Setup of the AE tensile testing. (a) Schematic diagram of the sensor arrangement; (b) photo of the sensors and the CFRP specimen; (c) neighborhood of the PSFBG was glued to the laminate; (d) the final damage stage in CFRP.

Figure 3. Cumulative AE hits obtained by the PZT sensor and PSFBG showing the Kaiser effect and different damage types.

Figure 4. Confirmation of the damage types in CFRP laminates. (a) Transverse cracking; (b) fiber breaking.

3 NOVEL FBG-EFL SENSING SYSTEM

3.1 Structures of ultrasonic FBG demodulated by EFL

Although PSFBG balanced sensing system introduced in section 2 has high sensitivity, its low robustness is a problem due to its narrow full-width-at-half-maximum (FWHM) (i.e., small dynamic range). In almost all the conventional ultrasonic OFSs, feedback controller is actually needed to stable the whole sensing system, resulting in complexity and high cost. In order to solve this universal problem, we demodulated the Bragg wavelength shift by using an EFL, differing from other ultrasonic FBG sensors demodulated by an independent semiconductor TLS. Figure 5(a-c) show three basic structures, referred to fiber laser-sensor 1-3 (FLS1-3) in this paper. Figure 5(d) shows the structure of the erbium doped fiber amplifier (EDFA) (FiberLabs, AMP-FL8013) used in our experiment, which was comprised of a section of erbium doped fiber (EDF), a 980-nm pump laser and a wavelength-division multiplexing (WDM). The input current of the pump laser was 150 mA in all the following experiment. The FLS1 and FLS2 had ring cavity, and FLS3 had linear cavity. The propagation direction of laser in cavity was marked by the dot arrow line in each figure. The FBGs used in FLS1 and FLS3 were normal FBG with 1.5-mm grating length and apodized FBG with 50-mm grating length (AFBG1); the FBGs used in FLS2 were apodized FBG with 20-mm grating length (AFBG2) and PSFBG with 5-mm grating length although its effective grating length was much shorter. All the FBGs had the same polyimide coating and the same diameter of 125 μm , manufactured by Fujikura, Ltd. Figure 6 shows the spectra and the key parameters of these FBGs, obtained by scanning a TLS (Agilent, 81682A). Because of their different grating lengths and different structures, the FBGs had different properties. For example, AFBG1 and PSFBG had narrower FWHMs compared to FBG and AFBG2, respectively; and AFBG2 had steeper slope than FBG. The FBG and AFBG1 were inserted into the EFL by circulators in the ring cavity of FLS1; however, the FBG and AFBG1 were directly used as reflectors of the resonator in the linear cavity of FLS3, leading to a simpler configuration. In every FLS, the laser light was lead out by an optical coupler and detected by a photo-detector (Thorlabs, PDA10CS-EC). In fact, the structure of the FLS3 could be further simplified and compacted by removing the optical coupler and directly detected the laser output from the FBGs because both the AFBG1 and FBG does not have 100% reflectivity.

Figure 5. Typical structures of novel FLS systems. (a) FLS1: ring cavity with normal FBG and AFBG1. (b) FLS2: ring cavity with AFBG2 and PSFBG. (c) FLS3: linear cavity with AFBG1 and FBG. (d) Typical EDFA.

Figure 6. Spectra and key parameters of the FBGs used in novel sensor design. (a) normal FBG; (b) AFBG1 with 50-mm grating length; (c) AFBG2 with 20-mm grating length; (d) PSFBG. L: grating length; R/T: reflectivity/transmittance.

3.2 Ultrasonic sensing principle

The principle of ultrasonic sensing of these FLSs is described. Firstly, the laser is established when the gain from the EDFA exceeds the in-cavity loss. The wavelength of the output laser is mainly determined by the Bragg wavelength of the FBG with relatively narrow FWHM, which is AFBG1 or PSFBG. The Bragg wavelengths of the FBG and AFBG2 are slightly different to those of the AFBG1 and PSFBG, e.g. the Bragg wavelength of the AFBG1 is close to the 3-dB position on the spectrum of the FBG in FLS1 and FLS3. When the spectrum of the FBG is shifted by the ultrasonic wave, the relative position of Bragg wavelength between FBG and AFBG1 will be changed, leading to the change of the laser in-cavity loss. Similarly, the laser in-cavity loss also changes when the PSFBG is shifted by the ultrasonic wave in FLS2. Generally, any physical parameter that can vary the relative position of Bragg wavelength between FBG pairs in these three FLSs can change the in-cavity loss, and subsequently change the laser output. As a result, the final voltage vibration from photo-detector reflects ultrasonic waveforms. To conclude this physical phenomenon, the ultrasonic detection based on FLS has four steps: 1) laser establishment, 2) Bragg wavelength shift by ultrasonic wave, 3) in-cavity loss change, 4) output vibration. Only when the first three steps are all satisfied, ultrasonic signal can be detected.

The light source and the sensor in these EFLs are actually integrated and mutually dependent, thus they show some interesting characteristics and advantages, mainly including: 1) seamless connection, 2) versatile functions, 3) high-performance sensing. Owing to the entirely fiber-based property of the EFL, it seamlessly connects to the FBG without other assistances, leading to a simple, integrated and rugged system, as well as low cost. Furthermore, FLS1 and 3 are able to single-ended access, which is very important to practical application. Especially FLS3 has possibility to be portable because of its simple structure and small number of components. Secondly, self-adjustment measurement or static/dynamic measurement can be accomplished just by selecting different installation methods. Self-adjustment measurement means the FLS could always detect ultrasonic signals no matter how the environmental quasi-static parameters (temperature or/and strain) change. Static/dynamic measurement means localized static parameters (strain or temperature) and dynamic parameters (ultrasonic wave) can be simultaneously measured. These versatile functions will be discussed later in this paper. Thirdly, high-performance sensing could be achieved. For example, the FLS2 which uses PSFBG has very high sensitivity and very broad bandwidth, and is able to detect ultrasonic signals

from actuator in real time as well as AE signals from material damage.

3.3 Calibration results

Before demonstrating the performance of the proposed sensing systems, the FBGs used in the experiment were calibrated. Figure 7(a) and (b) show the Bragg wavelength shifts of the four FBGs to temperature and strain, respectively. Temperature calibration was conducted by placing the FBGs in an oven whose temperature was measured using a thermocouple. Strain calibration was conducted through tensile testing, wherein the FBGs were glued onto a plastic plate, and the reference strain was measured using a foil strain gage attached close to the FBGs. The Bragg wavelength shifts were monitored by optical spectrum analyser (Anritsu, MS9710C). All four FBGs had linear responses to temperature change with similar slopes, fitting the theory [7]. Although the Bragg wavelength shifts of all four FBGs were also linearly proportional to the strain, the initial data deviated from the correct positions marked by the dot circle in Figure 7(b). It is believed that this was caused by the residual stress occurred during the FBG installation process. By repeating this calibration experiment, we found the temperature calibration results were almost constant, and also found the strain calibration results were relatively different, depending on the attachment conditions that were very difficult to manually control.

Figure 7. Bragg wavelength shifts of FBGs to (a) temperature and (b) strain.

3.4 Ultrasonic responses

In order to detect ultrasonic wave, in-cavity loss change caused by the relative Bragg wavelength shift in ultrasonic detection is a criterion. Different FBGs have different responses to high-frequency ultrasonic wave nevertheless with similar responses to static parameters. The theory of the effective grating length explains this effect. For example, the normal FBG due to its short grating length could be fully shifted by an ultrasonic strain; however the AFBG1 experiences this effect with less intensity because compression counteracts stretching when the grating length is longer than the wavelength of the ultrasonic signals. Same physical phenomena exist in the pair of PSFBG and AFBG2 because the effective grating length of PSFBG is very short and the grating length of AFBG2 is long. In a word, although influenced by the same ultrasonic signal, the Bragg wavelength shifts of FBGs are different, and cause the laser in-cavity loss change, and subsequently leading to the ultrasonic detectability. Thus, the ultrasonic responses of different FLSs are determined by the FBG sensors with short grating lengths, i.e., normal FBG or PSFBG.

The other effect that influences the ultrasonic responses of FLSs is the dynamic behavior of EFL, which is largely different from traditional ultrasonic FBG sensing system. The EFL is insensitive to the quasi-static change and low frequency vibration, but is very sensitive to the ultrasonic signal whose frequency is close to the frequency of the laser-inherent relaxation oscillation [8, 9]. In other words, the EFL can largely enhance the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the detected signal which has specific frequency. The frequency of the relaxation oscillation is determined by many laser parameters, such as the pump power, the resonator losses, the round-trip time of the resonator, the upper-state

lifetime of the gain medium, etc. Once an EFL is established, the other parameters will be fixed except the pump power which can be adjusted by the input current. Therefore, the most sensitive frequency of the system is adjustable to a certain extent.

3.5 Experimental setup

Figure 8 shows a typical experimental setup for demonstrating the performance of FLS1 system. The input signal was a three-cycle sin wave with Hamming window generated from a function generator (NF, WF1974). Its middle frequency was 30 kHz and its amplitude was 150 V enhanced by an electrical amplifier (NF, HSA4012). All the data were recorded by an oscilloscope (Yokogawa, DL708E). The CFRP laminate (T700S/2500, [45/0/-45/90]_{3s}, Toray Industries, Inc.) had dimension of 200×200×3.4 mm³. Figure 9 shows the detailed configuration of the CFRP laminate and the arrangement of the sensors. Along the diagonal of the CFRP laminate, we glued PZT transducers (Fuji Ceramic, 1045S) and FBGs by using high-acoustic-impedance ultrasonic couplant, and then used tapes to fix them. This commercial non-resonant PZT transducer with diameter of 20 mm had broad bandwidth approximately from 200 kHz to 1.3 MHz, and working temperature from -20 °C to 80 °C. The distance between the sensor and the actuator was 150 mm. We also glued the same type of PZT beside the FBG sensor for reference.

Figure 8. Experimental setup.

Figure 9. Configuration of CFRP specimen and arrangement of sensors.

In the experiment for self-adjustment measurement, FLS1 system was used. We glued FBG pair

(e.g., normal FBG and AFBG1 in FLS1) on the same position, as shown in Figure 9(b). Then we put the CFRP laminate with the sensors (FBGs and PZTs) in an oven whose temperature was monitored by a thermocouple, while kept the other devices and components outside for temperature isolation. Actually, because of the light weight and flexibility of optical fiber, remote ultrasonic detection can be easily achieved. On the other hand, in the experiment for static/dynamic measurement, we used FLS3 system. We only glued normal FBG on the CFRP, but attached AFBG1 on a plastic plate whose strain level was monitored by a foil strain gage attached close to the AFBG1. The wavelength of the AFBG1 was locked to the suitable position on the spectrum of the FBG by applying a strain on the plastic plate. Therefore, we detected ultrasonic signals from the output voltage change from the photo-detector and obtained the strain level on the AFBG to calculate the temperature of the CFRP laminate. Hence the versatile functions of the FLSs are mainly decided by the attachment method. i.e., FLS1 also can be used in static/dynamic measurement and FLS3 also can be used in self-adjustment measurement.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Ultrasonic detection by FLS

Figure 10 shows some typical waveforms detected by different ultrasonic OFSs, which are (a) normal FBG demodulated by TLS, (b) PSFBG demodulated by balanced sensing technique, and (c) FLS1 sensing system in self-adjustment measurement. Except the waveform in Figure 10(a) that is averaged value of 16384 repeats, the others are averaged value of 1024 repeats. The waveform detected by FLS1 has the highest SNR, and the one detected by normal FBG has the lowest SNR even when it has the maximum averaging times. Because the input ultrasonic frequency is close to the frequency of relaxation oscillation of this EFL when 980-nm pump current is 150 mA, the amplitude of the detected signal is largely amplified. The amplification effect from the relaxation oscillation is so significant that it makes the SNR of the waveform of FLS1 higher than that of PSFBG balanced sensing system although the slope of PSFBG is about 28 times higher than that of FBG. However, the side-effect of the relaxation oscillation is the waveform deformation, as seen from the differences between Figure 10(b) and (c). The actual waveform can be reconstructed by post data process method based on denoising and deconvolution, demonstrated in [10]. The reconstructed waveform (Figure 10(d)) is close to the actual one (Figure 10(b)), although its SNR decreases compared to the original waveform (Figure 10(c)).

Figure 10. Typical ultrasonic signals detected by different sensor: (a) Normal FBG; (b) PSFBG; (c) FLS1; (d) Reconstructed waveform.

Figure 11. CWT results of (a) ultrasonic signal from PSFBG and (b) reconstructed ultrasonic signal from FLS1.

We further conducted continuous wavelet transform (CWT) to analyze the time-frequency distributions of the ultrasonic signal from PSFBG and the reconstructed ultrasonic signal from FLS1, and showed the results in Figure 11(a) and (b), respectively. Both signals have the same arrival time, meaning the ultrasonic detection of FLS is due to the Bragg wavelength shift, the same as FBG or PSFBG ultrasonic sensor. The energy ranges of both signals are similar, in the range of 1 - 3 ms and 15 - 50 kHz, but their distributions are different. The large energy envelopes in the low frequency range in Figure 11(a) marked by two dot circles almost vanish in Figure 11(b). In contrast, the high-frequency energy envelopes in Figure 11(b) is very obvious. These different responses to different frequencies can be explained by the influence from the attachment method. Because both FBG and AFBG1 in FLS1 were attached on the same position of the target CFRP laminate, their Bragg wavelengths shift similarly when the ultrasonic frequency is relatively low (i.e., when ultrasonic wavelength is much longer than the grating length of FBG or AFBG), leading to the weak sensitivity in low frequency.

4.2 Versatile functions

Figure 12(a-c) show the ultrasonic signals detected by the reference PZT sensor, detected by the FLS1 for self-adjustment measurement, and detected by the FLS3 for static dynamic measurement, under different temperature conditions, respectively.

During temperature change from 25 °C to 85 °C shown in Figure 12(b), the Bragg wavelength of FBG will shift about 0.6 nm, which is larger than the linear slope area in its spectrum. As for normal FBG demodulation technique which uses external independent TLS, this large Bragg wavelength shift will be obviously out of the detectable range when a feedback controller is not used. However, the wavelength of our EFL critically follows this FBG wavelength no matter how the environmental static parameters change in an ideal condition. In other words, the laser in-cavity loss is constant, and consequently, the FBG sensor is always illuminated by in-built laser of the FLS. The demonstrated self-adjustment ability of FLSs shows its high practicability in SHM of composite when this material is being used in practice.

As shown in Figure 12(c), ultrasonic detection was also achieved in static/dynamic detection. According to the strain read from the reference strain gage, we calculate the temperature in the oven according to the calibration results, and show the results in Figure 13. Although the measured values and the actual values have some differences, they still roughly reflect the static environmental condition of the target CFRP laminate.

Figure 14 shows the comparison of the amplitude change of all the waves in Figure 12(a-c). The signals detected by PZT have very small amplitudes, the signals detected by FLSs, especially by FLS3, have large amplitudes, making it easier to be detected. Furthermore, the ultrasonic detection performances to all sensors degrade. The signal amplitude decrease of PZT transducer could be explained by its temperature-dependent sensitivity and the change of the couplant that becomes harder in high temperature. The signal amplitude decrease of FLSs is partially due to the performance degradation of the PZT actuator, as well as the couplant, and is also partially due to the slightly

different responses of FBGs to static parameters shown in Figure 7. Thus, the actual performance of the FLS depends on the attachment condition. In addition, the amplitudes of the signals from FLSs decrease more slowly than that from PZT sensor, demonstrating the better performances of the proposed FLSs in high temperature compared to conventional PZT sensor. For example, the amplitude of signal from FLS1 in 85 °C is about 33.3% of that in room temperature of 25 °C. In order to further improve the sensing performance of the FLSs, we suggest to manufacture a compact sensor head, such as by solidly fixing two FBGs together in order to improve the similarity of their static responses.

Figure 12. Amplitude changes with the increase of temperature: (a) PZT sensor; (b) FLS1; (c) FLS3.

Figure 13. Temperature measurement by FLS3 in static/dynamic simultaneous measurement.

Figure 14. Comparison between different sensors.

4.3 High-performance sensing

Because of the steep slope and short effective grating length of the PSFBG, the sensing system

based on this PSFBG which is FLS2 has the highest sensitivity and broadest bandwidth among all FLSs. Figure 15(a) shows the energy level of the detected ultrasonic signals and noises of traditional PZT sensor and FLS2 to different frequencies. These results were measured by using electrical spectrum analyzer (Advantest, R3131A) when the input signal was a continuous sin wave. Obviously, the FLS2 has much higher sensitivity than PZT sensor. The traditional PZT sensor almost cannot detect ultrasonic signal in some frequencies, such as about 2.5, 5 and 9.5 MHz, because the signal is nearly buried in the noise level. Whereas our novel FLS2 can detect ultrasonic signal at every frequency up to 10 MHz, which is very high to the application of ultrasonic SHM of composite. Figure 15(b) shows the SNR of different sensors after removing the influence from PZT actuator. The sensitivities of both sensors decrease when the frequency of the input signal increases. In addition, the sensitivity of PZT sensor shows resonant phenomena, however the sensitivity of our FLS2 is relative flat, which could make signal analysis easier in ultrasonic SHM.

Figure 15. FLS2 has high performance. (a) Ultrasonic signals and noises of different sensors to different frequencies. (b) SNR of different sensors to different frequencies.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, we reviewed a novel advanced ultrasonic OFS and its application in ultrasonic SHM of composites. In order to solve the universal problem of low robustness in conventional OFSs, a concept based on ultrasonic FBG demodulated by EFL was proposed. By changing the structure of EFL and selecting the suitable FBGs, different but versatile sensing systems can be designed. Although their fundamental physical phenomena are identical, each system has its own advantages, e.g., self-adjustment measurement, static/dynamic measurement, and high performance measurement, leading to different applications in ultrasonic SHM. Among this performance, self-adjustment ability of the FLS that can resistance temperature change from 25 °C to 85 °C is very interesting and has high practicability. According to different and specific requirements in certain cases, we could select the most suitable design and obtained the high reliable ultrasonic data.

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